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The Intergenerational Climate of Spanish University Research

The knowledge economy has transformed society and the university environment, which has moved towards the market model. The profound changes produced under this new model have had implications for institutional functions, especially research. In Spain, this transformation has also coincided with the intergenerational overlap of researchers. Consequently, research on intergenerational relations has become an area of interest and concern. This study analysed the intergenerational climate of Spanish research by administering the Workplace Intergenerational Climate Scale. This questionnaire is divided into five subscales, namely, lack of generational stereotypes, positive intergenerational affect, intergenerational contact, workplace generational inclusiveness, and workplace intergenerational retention. In total, 2003 researchers from 10 Spanish public universities participated in this study. The findings suggest a favourable intergenerational climate in Spanish research, albeit with some generational stereotypes. Older researchers (Baby Boomers and Generation X) showed the most positive perception of the various aspects of the intergenerational climate of Spanish research, represented by the different subscales.

Keywords: intergenerational climate, intergenerational relationships, higher education, research, researchers

INTRODUCTION

In the Spanish context, universities have three basic functions—teaching, research, and knowledge transfer. These functions have been greatly affected by recent changes to the model of higher education institutions, which have moved from a model with shared bureaucratic (strong administrative dependence) and academic (internal control through certain collegiate structures) characteristics towards a decidedly market model (Carvalho and Videira 2019). The market model stands out in its greater openness to societal

demands, efficiency-oriented management, institutional identity that favours differentiation between universities (Pinheiro and Stensaker 2014), closer links between the university, labour market, and economic system (Gornitzka, Maassen, and de Boer 2017), and, lastly, research intensification among academic staff (Wilkins, Hazzam, and Leanb 2021).

Research is possibly the function that has most and best adapted to the market-oriented university because, in a context with knowledge as the predominant value, university research is the key to economic development. As stated by Lucas (2009), in recent decades, universities have been establishing a culture focused on academic capitalism to meet the scientific and technological innovation needs of the economy. In some manner, the market model links research output to economic development and reveals deep interactions between economic dynamics and research (Jaffe et al. 2020). This phenomenon is the origin of the knowledge economy, and it enables a deeper understanding of the role that research may play in shaping the economy and identifying reference resource allocations across all disciplines.

Under the market model, university research has changed in both academic and organisational terms. Castro and Ion (2019) highlighted a context that increasingly values the generation of economic income and focuses on professional development, which is externally evaluated based on research output. These effects on organisations result in increased internationalisation, diversification of funding sources, collaborations between the government, the business sector, and the university, and the emergence of networking and research groups.

Various generations of researchers currently coexist in Spanish universities, although their age groups differ between authors (Edge 2014; Edge, Descours, and Frayman 2016).

Nevertheless, the following generations can be identified: Baby Boomers (55 to 73 years), Generation X (39 to 54 years), Generation Y, also known as Millennials (23 to 38 years), and Generation Z (up to 22 years). During the 2021–2022 academic year, 129,904 researchers worked in Spain. Their average age was 49.4 years, although it rose to 55.6 years when including only lecturers, readers, and professors (Ministerio de Universidades 2022). These figures highlight the notable aging of the teaching staff, which can also be explained by extended cuts in public spending lasting several years and resulting from different economic crises. Compounding this issue is the fact that public policies capable of reversing this situation have not been promoted in all Spanish higher education institutions.

Researchers have been working primarily in research groups, suggesting that staff of different generations interact in these groups. For this reason, a good organisational climate favourable to intergenerational relationships must be promoted for enhancing research performance. Intergenerational relationships are inherent to the human condition and derive from interactions between members of different generations who live in the same period (Núñez, Míguez, and García 2018). In a society characterised by generational distance (Zaidi, Gasior, and Manchin 2012), universities must find new forms of collaboration and solidarity between generations (Gutiérrez and Hernández 2013). Each generation meets the demands and needs of other generations and contributes and receives something from them in return (Albuérne and Juanco 2002). In fact, intergenerational relationships have been promoted for some time now, and the United Nations World Assembly on Aging has already expressed the convenience of supporting intergenerational solidarity through measures that favour exchange between different age groups (UN 2002).

Researchers who work in groups comprising members of heterogeneous ages build social capital by occupying central positions in the community, and they are more effective than researchers who work individually (Rotolo and Petruzzelli 2012). The interaction between people of different ages benefits society. In addition, good intergenerational contact improves the attitudes of younger generations towards more experienced generations and vice versa (Canedo, García, and Pacheco 2017; Gerpott, Lehmann-Willenbrock, and Voelpel 2017). In turn, based on the dynamics of social influence on organisations, Perkmann et al. (2021) explained that researchers are part of a community that influences their behaviour and engagement, professional development, and research output in both quantity and quality. Differences in the beliefs, values, and priorities of each generation have implications for professional development, workplace communication, and interpersonal relationships (Kaye, Scheff, and Thielfoldt 2003; Kazak and Polat 2018; Zemke, Raines, and Filipczak 2000). Moreover, generational differences between researchers can influence their professional success (Portela et al. 2020). In short, understanding is facilitated by the maintenance of relationships and sharing of experiences between workers of various generations (Bagnasco et al. 2020; Boström and Schmidt-Hertha 2017; Çağlar and Soner 2022). Moreover, workplace sensitivity and collaboration are fostered and cultural and human enrichment is improved between generations through information exchange and knowledge transfer.

Despite advances in the analysis of intergenerational relationships, few studies have delved into the intergenerational climate among academics conducting research, which makes it difficult to identify the factors that improve intergenerational relationships. Our study aims at analysing the intergenerational climate of Spanish university research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A survey-based descriptive study was conducted using an ex post facto methodology. The fieldwork was performed between February and July 2021, and it consisted of a self-administered online questionnaire sent to a sample of 2003 researchers working in Spanish universities. A maximum margin of error of 2% was accepted, with a 95% confidence level ($p = q = 0.50$ and $k = 2$). Before filling in the questionnaire, all participants signed the informed consent form, which clearly stated that their participation was free and voluntary, that they could leave the study at any time, and that their anonymity and data protection were ensured. Table 1 outlines the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants.

[Insert Table 1 here]

The self-administered questionnaire entitled The Workplace Intergenerational Climate Scale (WICS), which measures attitudes and perceptions of members of an organisation regarding other colleagues of different ages at their workplace, was used (King and Bryant 2017). Originally, the questionnaire consists of 20 items grouped into 5 subscales, namely, lack of generational stereotypes (LGS), positive intergenerational affect (PIA), intergenerational contact (IC), workplace generational inclusiveness (WGI), and workplace intergenerational retention (WIR). In the version of the questionnaire that we used in this study, all items were scored on a 7-point Likert scale (1 for ‘strongly disagree’ and 7 for ‘strongly agree’, except for the IC subscale, in which 1 was ‘never’ and 7 was ‘always’).

First, the variables determining each WICS subscale (i.e. LGS, PIA, IC, WGI, and WIR) were subjected to descriptive data analysis. Second, the means were compared using the F statistic (Miller 1981; Toothaker 1991) to assess initial differences as a function of the selected comparison variables (i.e., gender, generation, position, knowledge field, and

university size). Welch's correction was used when the variance was not homogeneous (as determined by Levene's test; Tomarken and Serlin 1986). In the analysis of more than two comparison categories, Tukey's *post-hoc* honestly significant difference (HSD) tests were used under homogeneity of variance, and Games-Howell correction was used when this condition was not met.

RESULTS

The information provided by researchers from Spanish universities (hereinafter the researchers) indicates that, in general (Table 2), no generational stereotypes exist in research groups despite differences in ways of working depending on age (means [m]=3.84).

Researchers usually feel comfortable working and interacting with colleagues from other generations, as indicated by m ranging from 6.31 (standard deviation [SD]=1.22) to 5.57 (SD=1.73). These data are in line with the high scores on the degree of intergenerational inclusion (from m=6.16 [SD=1.35] to m=5.23 [SD=1.91]).

As for WIR, although these scores are high as well, and none of the generations feels pressured by others to surrender their responsibilities (m=6.5, SD=1.26 and m=6.39, SD=1.46), some of the youngest researchers are ignored in promotion and communication processes, based on their perception.

The analysis of the frequency of intergenerational contact shows that interactions beyond purely work-related issues, such as conversations about non-work issues (m=4.55, SD=1.83) and personal lives (m=3.89, SD=1.86) and lunches with colleagues from other generations (m=3.38, SD=2.09), are few.

[Insert Table 2 here]

The aggregate results of each subscale of the WICS questionnaire (Table 3) confirm that, overall, the intergenerational climate of researchers is positive. However, the LGS subscale, with a mean of 5.06 (SD=1.24) on a 7-point Likert scale, and IC subscale, with a mean of 4.39 (SD=1.44), scored slightly lower than the other subscales.

[Insert Table 3 here]

The organisational climate, which was focused on intergenerational relationships in this study, is a highly complex organisational dimension subject to a wide variety of factors (Powell et al. 2021; Schneider, Ehrhart, and Macey 2013). However, the significant differences were, overall, not particularly important despite some noteworthy nuances. Below, we review these differences by generation, gender, and position of currently employed university researchers and by university size.

The analysis by generation (i.e. Baby Boomers, Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z), which was one of the main variables of this study, showed significant differences in four of the five subscales of the WICS questionnaire (Table 4). The *post-hoc* tests indicated that Baby Boomers and Generation X have a lower perception of generational stereotypes and, coherently, appreciate intergenerational relationships (i.e. PIA and WGI) more positively than Millennials. In turn, when focusing on the frequency of intergenerational contact, we found significant differences between Generation Z, Baby Boomers, and Generation X. Again, the latter two generations (m=4.47, SD=1.33 and m=4.53, SD=1.44, respectively) identify a higher frequency of intergenerational interaction than Generation Z researchers (m=3.86, SD=1.53).

[Insert Table 4 here]

As Table 5 shows, gender was the only variable without significant differences in the

intergenerational climate of Spanish university research as a function of the category (i.e. male, female, and non-binary) under study.

[Insert Table 5 here]

In the university context, position is usually directly associated with age and, therefore, with the generation of the researcher. Hence, some coincidences were detected between the variation in this variable and the generation variable discussed above (Table 6). In the three subscales with significant differences, the *post-hoc* tests indicated that professors and associate professors have slightly more positive perceptions of the intergenerational climate (LGS, PIA, and IC) in their research groups and centres than do pre-doc researchers. Similarly, the perception of pre-doc researchers was also significantly lower than that of other researchers with positions closer to theirs, such as assistant lecturers, in the PIA and IC subscales, and that of post-doctoral researchers in the IC subscale. In addition, the perception of adjunct lecturers stood out as the most common position in the Spanish university research context. Although the differences were very subtle, these staff perceived a less positive intergenerational climate than did other researchers with a permanent position, such as associate professors (LGS, PIA, and IC) and professors (PIA and IC).

[Insert Table 6 here]

University size usually has a strong effect on the variation of other variables and organisational phenomena (Bloch 2022; Talacchi 1960). However, in this study, the differences identified were not relevant and only significant in two subscales, namely, WGI and IC (Table 7). More specifically, regarding WGI, researchers from medium-sized universities (between 25,000 and 40,000 students) have a slightly more negative

perception ($m=5.64$, $SD=1.29$) than do researchers from small (less than 25,000 students) and large (more than 40,000 students) universities. Similarly, researchers from medium-sized universities also have a lower perception of IC ($m=4.27$, $SD=1.47$) than do their colleagues from large universities ($m=4.48$, $SD=1.43$).

[Insert Table 7 here]

The results from the analysis by field of knowledge only showed significant differences in two subscales, namely, WGI and IC (Table 8). In general, Health Science researchers have a slightly more positive perception of WGI and IC than do researchers from Arts and Humanities and Social Sciences. Similarly, the perception of IC of researchers in Science and Bioscience ($m=4.47$, $SD=1.35$) and Engineering and Architecture ($m=4.55$, $SD=1.42$) were found to differ significantly from that of researchers in the field of Arts and Humanities ($m=4.11$, $SD=1.49$).

[Insert Table 8 here]

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

One feature of current organisations is the increasing interaction between age-diverse workers as the workforce gradually ages in most industrialised economies as a result of demographic changes (Gerpott and Fasbender 2020). In this context, universities have been adapting to the knowledge economy, wherein research is the predominant value. In addition, the economic situation of universities has also worsened owing to the latest economic crises. The result is a staff in which up to four different generations coexist for the first time and researchers with different values, expectations, and perceptions work together (Lyons and Kuron 2014). These differences affect performance, collaborations,

learning, social relationships, and especially workplace climate (Weston 2001).

Therefore, they are a strategic challenge for universities. These institutions must learn how to maximise the benefits of intergenerational work, including knowledge exchange, talent retention, collaborations, professional development, and informal learning, especially considering the strong and positive relationship between intergenerational knowledge sharing, worker learning, and education organisational climate (Çelik and Polat 2022).

The intergenerational climate of Spanish universities is suitable for research, as shown, primarily because of the absence of actions involving pressure between groups and the positive perception of communication and social interaction processes, which accounts for the high level of intergenerational affection. The researchers' perception of the intergenerational climate is more strongly determined by their academic rank or level than by their gender. Hence, researchers of younger generations have a less positive perception of the intergenerational climate than do researchers with a permanent position, with non-significant gender differences in this perception. These data corroborate the findings of Christian et al. (2021) in the field of medicine, who concluded that the main concerns of early-career researchers are the lack of support from senior researchers, the appropriation of their ideas or work, and the poor workplace dynamics at universities. Nevertheless, despite numerous studies on differences in biases experienced by men and women during their research career (output, access to scientific management positions, glass ceiling, and working conditions, among others), such as the study by Huang et al. (2020), no gender differences in intergenerational climate were found in this study.

Conversely, in line with Scherer et al. (2021), we found that higher education disciplines frame the professional culture of researchers based on specific values and different

behaviours. Hence, researchers from Science, Bioscience, Engineering, and Architecture have a better perception of IC than do their colleagues from Arts and Humanities, and Health Science researchers have a better perception of WGI than do researchers from Social Sciences and Arts and Humanities.

Age not only determines the specific generation to which an individual belongs, but also has other implications for job stability and security, tenure track, institutional trajectory, and the professional (and life) development stage, among others. In short, the different manifestations of intergenerational climate are not only attributable to age, but also to its implications for academic development (Waaiker 2015).

These implications are valid for generational stereotypes as well. Despite differences in the ways of conducting research between generations, not too many generational stereotypes were perceived, and the few that emerged were identified in the youngest generations, that is, Millennials and Generation Y. For this reason, as they advance in their career, late-career (and older) researchers perceive fewer generational stereotypes than do early-career (and younger) researchers. The pressure to publish and the need for research output to which novice researchers are subjected, which is typical of market-oriented universities, could explain this situation. The possibility of establishing collaborations between researchers of different generations may be an appropriate strategy for reducing stereotypes, as explained by Wilkins, Hazzam, and Leanb (2021), who determined that many early-career researchers appreciate the benefits of networking and collaborating with established and successful researchers as they seek to demonstrate their legitimacy and achieve their professional goals. Therefore, by working in research groups with members of different ages, they may be able undertake more complex studies, which would be otherwise unfeasible if conducted individually, and reduce their

levels of stress and burnout, which commonly occurs in higher education.

Although each generation is defined by different identities and subcultures (Kuyken 2012), researchers reported feeling comfortable working with colleagues from other generations and regarded these intergenerational experiences as beneficial. Baby Boomers and Generation X researchers, in particular, enjoy working and interacting with researchers from younger generations. The idea that working with researchers of the same generation is better is not prevalent. Moreover, we agree with Albuerte and Juanco (2002), who highlighted the need for each generation to become aware that they should meet the demands and needs of other generations, contributing and receiving something from the others in return. Both younger and more experienced scholars should share the responsibility for motivating and encouraging each other when collaborating for research purposes (Wilkins, Hazzam, and Lean 2021).

Overall, WGI is positively perceived by researchers, and it gradually improves with age. In other words, Baby Boomers have a better perception of their work environment, respect among colleagues, and communication processes than do Generation Z researchers. This perception may be explained by the lack of equity in academic communication processes and availability of channels or access to sources for the entire community despite the intensive use of technology among the youngest researchers. In a study with 434 members of academic staff, Kleinhans et al. (2015) found that a growing body of evidence has highlighted differences in workplace ethics and communication styles between the four generations. Addressing these differences is crucial for closing possible workplace generational gaps and contributing to intergenerational learning and to the discovery of new and different ways of thinking and solving problems and conflicts (Hahn 2011; Polat and Kazak 2015). For this reason, different communication strategies

must be considered, recognised, and valued by all (de Blois and Lagacé 2017).

The WICS subscale that was perceived best among researchers is WIR, which is specified in the nature of social interactions between generations by not forcing, pressuring, displacing, or ignoring researchers from other generations, among other actions. Thus, researchers do not feel pressured to promote or surrender their responsibilities. This perspective was also highlighted by Sumbal et al. (2017) when considering that eliminating fear and reinforcing confidence and job security are the keys to WIR in the business sector. Not doing so causes Generation X and Generation Y professionals to quit their jobs, as shown by Lavoie-Tremblay et al. (2010) in their study on the health sector.

The present study of the intergenerational climate of Spanish research also included communication aspects and social and informal interactions (IC), which are the most complex and difficult goals to achieve among the WICS subscales. Intergenerational informal and social spaces are not perceived as an advantage, especially among the youngest generations. Accordingly, they tend to interact informally with members of the same generation and to a lesser extent with older colleagues. Developing a better intergenerational climate requires the exchange of knowledge and experiences (Kuyken, Ebrahimi, and Saives 2018) among the professionals of an organisation while promoting collaboration (Kazak and Polat 2018). Therefore, researchers should interact with colleagues from other generations because it would help them understand their co-workers (Bagnasco et al. 2020; Çağlar and Soner 2022).

One of the limitations of this study derives from the nature of the organisational climate, which is constantly changing and requires the consideration of longitudinal data to test temporal relationships and generation of new data by assessing other types of universities

(i.e. private universities or those outside the top of the national ranking), according to Obeng et al. (2021). Nevertheless, the intergenerational climate has clearly become a priority on the university agenda. For this reason, universities must continue to improve and develop their intergenerational climate in research settings. In this regard, certain specific strategies could be implemented, such as those proposed by Leon (2020), which aim at culture development (volunteering and storytelling) or staff satisfaction (mentoring and training). Gairín (2020) proposed exchange and collaboration strategies such as establishing knowledge sharing and transfer agendas, age and talent management plans, generational exchange programs, knowledge maps, and intergenerational workshops. Additionally, Sumbal et al. (2017) advocated building professional communities comprising people of different ages and trajectories as the most reasonable solution and appropriate strategy for intergenerational work.

A positive intergenerational climate of research leads to improvements at the individual, group, and institutional levels (King et al. 2019). Considering these benefits, higher education institutions should regularly diagnose and improve their intergenerational climate towards overcoming generational stereotypes, which often result more from intuitions and beliefs than from actual and confirmed difficulties (Hirsh 2020).

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Declaration of interest statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

REFERENCES

- Albuerne, Fernando, and Angeles Juanco. 2002. "Intergeneracionalidad y escuela: trabajamos juntos, aprendemos juntos." *Revista Interuniversitaria de Formación del Profesorado* 45: 77-88.
- Bagnasco, Anamaria, Mark Hayter, Silvia Rossi, Milko Zanini, Ramona Pellegrini, Giuseppe Aleo, Gianluca Catania, and Loredana Sasso. 2020. "Experiences of participating in intergenerational interventions in older people's care settings: A systematic review and meta-synthesis of qualitative literature." *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 76 (1): 22-33. [doi/10.1111/jan.14214](https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.14214)
- Bloch, Roland. 2022. "Performing size. On the effects of 'critical mass' in science." *Globalisation, Societies and Education* 20 (4): 450-462. doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2021.1992751
- Boström, Ann-Kristin, and Bernhard Schmidt-Hertha. 2017. "Intergenerational Relationships and Lifelong Learning." *Journal of Intergenerational Relationships* 15 (1): 1-3. doi.org/10.1080/15350770.2017.1260408
- Çağlar, Çelik, and Soner Polat. 2022. "The relationship between intergenerational knowledge sharing and intergenerational learning levels among teachers." *Journal of Intergenerational Relationships*. Advance online publication. doi.org/10.1080/15350770.2022.2084202
- Canedo, Alejandro, Jesús-Nicasio García, and Deilis-Inonne Pacheco-Sanz. 2017. "A systematic review of the effectiveness of intergenerational programs." *Frontiers in Psychology* 8 (1882): 1-13. doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01882
- Carvalho, Teresa and Pedro Videira. 2019. "Losing autonomy? Restructuring Higher Education Institutions governance and relations between teaching and non-teaching staff." *Studies in Higher Education* 44 (4): 762-773. doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2017.1401059
- Castro, Diego, and Georgeta Ion. 2019. "Changes in the University Research Approach: Challenges for Academics' Scientific Productivity." *Higher Education Policy* 32: 681-699. doi.org/10.1057/s41307-018-0101-0
- Christian, Katherine, Carolyn Johnstone, JoAnn Larkins, Wendy Wright, and Michael Doran. 2021. "A survey of early-career researchers in Australia." *Elife* 10: 1-19 DOI: doi.org/10.7554/eLife.60613
- de Blois, Sarah, and Martine Lagacé. 2017. "Understanding Older Canadian Workers' Perspectives on Aging in the Context of Communication and Knowledge Transfer." *Canadian Journal of Communication* 42 (4): 631-644. doi:10.22230/cjc.2017v42n4a3071
- Edge, Karen. 2014. "A review of the empirical generations at work research: implications for school leaders and future research." *School Leadership & Management* 34 (2): 136-155. doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2013.869206

Edge, Karen, Katherine Descours, and Keren Frayman. 2016. "Generation X school leaders as agents of care: leader and teacher perspectives from Toronto, New York City and London." In *How School Leaders Contribute to Student Success*, edited by Leithwood, Kenneth, Jingping Sun, and Katina Pollock, 175-202. Cham: Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc6020008>

Gairín, Joaquín. 2020. "La gestión del conocimiento intergeneracional." In *La nueva gestión del conocimiento*, edited by Gairín, Joaquín, Cecilia Suárez and Anna Díaz, 229-280. Madrid: Wolters Kluwer.

Gerpott, Fabiola, Nale Lehmann-Willenbrock, and Sven Voelpel. 2017. "A phase model of intergenerational learning in organizations." *Academic of Management Learning & Education* 16 (2): 193-216. doi: doi.org/10.5465/amle.2015.0185

Gerpott, Fabiola, and Ulrike Fasbender. 2020. "Intergenerational Learning in Age-Diverse Meetings: A Social Comparison Perspective." Chap. 20 in *Managing Meetings in Organizations*, edited by Meinecke, Annika L., Joseph A. Allen, and Nale Lehmann-Willenbrock, 185-206. Bingley: Emerald Publishing. doi.org/10.1108/S1534-085620200000020009

Gornitzka, Aser, Peter Maassen, and Harry de Boer. 2017. "Change in university governance structures in continental Europe." *Higher Education Quarterly* 71 (3): 274-289. doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12127

Gutiérrez, Marta, and Daniel Hernández. 2013. "Las relaciones intergeneracionales en la sociedad actual: un imperativo necesario." *Educación Social. Revista de Intervención Socioeducativa* 55: 135-145.

Hahn, Joyce. 2011. "Managing multiple generations: scenarios from the workplace." *Nursing Forum* 46 (3): 119-127. doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6198.2011.00223.x

Hirsch, Peter Buell. 2020. "Follow the dancing meme: intergenerational relations in the workplace." *Journal of Business Strategy* 41(3): 67-71. doi.org/10.1108/JBS-02-2020-0034

Huang, Junming Alexander Gates, Roberta Sinatra, and Albert-László Barabási. 2020. "Historical comparison of gender inequality in scientific careers across countries and disciplines." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117 (9): 4609-4616. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1914221117>

Jaffe, Klaus, Enrique Horst, Laura H. Gunn, Juan Diego Zambrano, and Germán Molina. 2020. "A network analysis of research productivity by country, discipline and wealth." *PLOS ONE* 15 (5): e0232458. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0232458>

Kaye, Beverly, Devon Scheef, and Diane Thielfoldt. 2003. "Engaging the generations." *Human Resources in the 21st Century*, edited by Effrom, Marc, Robert Gandossy, and Marshall Goldsmith, 25-34. New York: Wiley.

- Kazak, Ender and Soner Polat. 2018. "School administrators' instructional leadership behaviours, intergenerational atmosphere, and intergenerational learning in schools." *Journal of Intergenerational Relationships* 16 (4): 441-462. doi.org/10.1080/15350770.2018.1489330
- King, Eden, Lisa Finkelstein, Thomas, Courtney, and Abby Corrington. 2019. "Generational differences at work are small. Thinking they're big effects our behavior." *Harvard Business Review* 1: 1-7
- King, Scott, and Fred Bryant. 2017. "The Workplace Intergenerational Climate Scale (WICS): A self-report instrument measuring ageism in the workplace." *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 38 (1): 124-151. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2118>
- Kleinhans, Kelly A., Kala Chakradhar, Susan Muller, and Paula Waddill. 2015. "Multigenerational perceptions of the academic work environment in Higher Education in the United States." *Higher Education* 70 (1): 89-103.
- Kuyken, Kerstin. 2012. "Knowledge communities: Towards a re-thinking of intergenerational knowledge transfer." *VINE: The Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems* 42 (3-4): 365- 381. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03055721211267495>
- Kuyken, Kerstin, Mehran Ebrahimi, and Anne-Laure S'aives. 2018. Towards a taxonomy of intergenerational knowledge transfer practices: Insights from an international comparison (Germany – Quebec)." *Learning Organization* 25 (2): 81–91. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TLO-02-2017-0023>
- Lavoie-Tremblay, Melanie, Maxime Paquet, Marie-Anik Duchesne, Anelise Santo, Ana Gavranic, François Courcy, and Serge Gagnon. 2010. "Retaining Nurses and Other Hospital Workers: An Intergenerational Perspective of the Work Climate: Intergenerational Perspective and Work Climate." *Journal of Nursing Scholarship* 42 (4): 414-422. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1547-5069.2010.01370.x>
- Leon, Ramona-Diana. 2020 "Fostering intergenerational learning in the hotel industry: A multiple criteria decision-making model." *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 91(1): 1-11. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102685
- Lucas, Lisa. 2009. "Research management and research cultures: power and productivity." In *Academic research and researchers*, edited by Brew, Angela, and Lisa Lucas, 36-48. Maidenhead: McGraw-Hill International.
- Lyons, Sean, and Lisa Kuron. 2014. "Generational differences in the workplace: a review of the evidence and directions for future research." *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 35 (S1): S139-S157. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.1913>
- Miller, Rupert. 1981. *Simultaneous statistical inference*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Ministerio de Universidades. 2022. *Estadística de personal de las universidades. Curso 2020-2021*. Gobierno de España: Madrid. Available: <https://cutt.ly/2K8Gwni>

- Núñez, Jessica, Gabriela Míguez, and Jesús García. 2018. "Las relaciones intergeneracionales y los procesos educativos en la familia." Paper presented at the *Internacional Congres SIPS*, Palma de Mallorca, Universitat Illes Balears.
- Obeng, Anthony, Yongyue Zhu, Samuel Azinga, and Prince Quansah. 2021. "Organizational Climate and Job Performance: Investigating the Mediating Role of Harmonious Work Passion and the Moderating Role of Leader–Member Exchange and Coaching." *Sage Open* 11 (2): 1-35. doi.org/10.1177/21582440211008456
- Perkmann, Markus, Rossella Salandra, Valentina Tartari, Maureen McKelvey, and Alan Hughes. 2021. "Academic Engagement: A Review of the Literature 2011-19". *Research Policy* 50 (1): 104114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104114>
- Pinheiro, Romulo and Bjorn Stensaker. 2014. "Designing the entrepreneurial university: The interpretation of a global idea." *Public Organization Review* 14 (4): 497-516.
- Polat, Soner and Ender Kazak. 2015. Primary School Teachers' Views on Intergenerational Learning." *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice* 15 (5): 1189-1203.
- Portela, Antonio, Ana Torres, Juan-Antonio Salmerón, and Silvia Martínez. 2020. "Generational diversity: relevance for professional collaboration in organizational and educational contexts". In *Generational diversity and intergenerational collaboration among teachers: perspectives and experience*, edited by Dorczak, Roman, and Antonio Portela. 137-152, Krakow: Uniwersytetu Jagiellonskiego.
- Powell, Byron, Kayne Mettert, Caitlin Dorsey, Bryan Weiner, Cameo Stanick, Rebeca Lengnick-Hall, and Cara Lewis. 2021. "Measures of organizational culture, organizational climate, and implementation climate in behavioral health: A systematic review." *Implementation Research and Practice* 2: 1-29. doi.org/10.1177/26334895211018862
- Rotolo, Danielle and Antonio Petruzzelli. 2012. "When does centrality matter? Scientific productivity and the moderating role of research specialization and cross-community ties." *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 34 (5): 648-670. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.1822>
- Scherer, Ronny, Sarah K. Howard, Jo Tondeur, and Fazilat Siddiq. 2021. "Profiling teachers' readiness for online teaching and learning in higher education: Who's ready?" *Computers In Human Behavior* 118: 106675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106675>
- Schneider, Benjamin, Mark Ehrhart, and William Macey. 2013. "Organizational climate and culture." *Annual Review of Psychology* 64 (1): 361-388.
- Sumbal, Muhammad Saleem, Eric Tsui, Eric See-to, and Andrew Barendrecht. 2017. "Knowledge retention and aging workforce in the oil and gas industry: a multi perspective study." *Journal of Knowledge Management* 21 (4): 907-924. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2016-0281>

- Talacchi, Sergio. 1960. "Organization size, individual attitudes and behavior: An empirical study." *Administrative Science Quarterly* 5 (3): 398-420. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2390663>
- Tomarken, Andrew and Ronald C. Serlin. 1986. "Comparison of ANOVA alternatives under variance heterogeneity and specific noncentrally structures." *Psychological Bulletin* 99: 90-99. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.99.1.90>
- Toothaker, Larry. 1991. *Multiple comparisons for researchers*. Newbury Park (CA): Sage.
- United Nations. 2002. *Informe de la Segunda Asamblea Mundial sobre el Envejecimiento*. New York: United Nations. Available <https://cutt.ly/BK5strp>
- Waaiker, Cathelij. 2015. "The coming of age of the academic career: Differentiation and professionalization of German academic positions from the 19th century to the present." *Minerva* 53 (1): 43-67. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43548972>
- Weston, Marta. 2001. "Coaching generations in the workplace". *Nursing Administration Quarterly* 25 (2): 11-21.
- Wilkins, Stehen, Joe Hazzam, and Jonathan Lean Leanb. 2021. "Doctoral publishing as professional development for an academic career in higher education." *The International Journal of Management Education* 19 (1): 1-13. doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100459
- Zaidi, Asghar, Katrin Gasior, and Robert Manchin. 2012. "Population Aging and Intergenerational Solidarity: International Policy Frameworks and European Public Opinion." *Journal of Intergenerational Relationships* 10 (3): 214-227. doi.org/10.1080/15350770.2012.697845
- Zemke, Ron, Claire Raines, and Bob Filipczak. 2000. *Generations at work: Managing the clash of Veterans, Boomers, Xers, and Nexters in your workplace*. New York: American Management Association. Available: <https://cutt.ly/QLwb4HL>